

Influence of planting time on gall midge incidence at Aduthurai

P. Karuppuchamy, S. Uthamasamy, and G. Chakkaravarthy, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612 101, Tamil Nadu, India

Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* incidence was measured on CO 40 in the samba season and on IR20 in the thaladi season. Plot size was 50 m² with 4 replications. The number of silvershoots in total tillers was counted.

During the samba season, maximum gall midge incidence was on the crop planted 1 September 1981 followed by crops planted on 16 September and 16 August (see figure). Incidence was less on crops planted on 2 and 17 October. During the thaladi season, maximum incidence was on the crop planted 16 September.

The 50- to 70-day-old crop in the samba season and the 30- to 60-day-old crop in the thaladi season were more prone to gall midge infestation.

Gall midge incidence (%)

Gall midge incidence during samba and thaladi seasons in Tamil Nadu, India.

Pests of hill rice in West Bengal, India

P. K. Banerjee and P. B. Chatterjee, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712 102, West Bengal, India

Rice is grown in the hilly areas of Darjeeling district on bench terraces up to 1,335 m altitude. Annual precipita-

tion ranges from 2,800 to 3,900 mm. The annual maximum temperatures range from 15° to 24° C and minimum temperatures from 75° to 19° C depending on the altitude. Only one medium to late duration rice crop is grown during the monsoon season. Economically important insect pests of hill rice are in the table. ■

Insect pests of hill rice in West Bengal, India.

Insect	Seasonal incidence	Economic importance
Stem borers		
White stem borer <i>Scirpophaga innotata</i> (Walker)	Jul-Oct, peak season in September	Damage varies from 30% to 80% of tillers.
Gold-fringed borer <i>Chilo auricilia</i> (Dudgeon)		
Rice bug		
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> (Thunberg)	Aug-Oct	Loss estimated at 25-35% of panicles.
Green leafhopper		
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)		
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål.)	Jul-Oct	Minor.
Big white leafhopper		
<i>Tettigella spectra</i> Distant	Oct-Nov	Minor.
Leaf folder		
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guenee)	Sep-Nov	At altitudes from 650-1000 m about 25-40% leaves damaged. Late crop most damaged.
Gall midge		
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Aug-Oct	At altitudes below 1000 m, 25-30% silvershoots.
Swarming caterpillar		
<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisduval)	Jul-Aug	Humid areas near perennial springs at lower altitudes are more infested, seedling damage.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Other pests

Hirschmanniella oryzae and other nematodes found in rice paddies of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

Dang-ngoc Kinh and Bui-yan Ngoc, Plant Protection Department, University of Hanoi, Vietnam

Seven species of nematodes have been found in rice plants and soil in the Mekong Delta: *Dirylenchus angustus*, *Aphelenchoides besseyi*, *Meloidogyne*

graminicola, *Hirschmanniella oryzae* spp., *Criconemella* sp., *Tybenchorhynchus* sp., *Helicotylenchus* sp.

Populations of *H. oryzae* were studied from about 1,000 soil samples and rice roots from 100 paddy fields. Sampling was done from tillering in the 1981 rainy season main crop to tillering in the 1982 second crop. Main crop varieties were Tau-bun, Tauchen, Nang-quot, Chum-ran, Gay-xe, Chet-cut, Lem-lun, Bang-senx. Second crop varieties were IR36,